

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF A COMPOSITE PATCH REINFORCEMENT SYSTEM FOR A MARINE APPLICATION CASE

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of composite materials in marine structures provides a great potential to reduce the weight and fuel consumption, minimize corrosion and structural defects and thereby to reduce the maintenance and overall operation costs of the vessel.

Balcony opening corners are prone to fatigue initiated cracking due to the stress concentration found around geometry discontinuities. Thus these areas are always designed with a radius to smoothen out the discontinuities and often have to be reinforced to prevent cracking. These balcony corners are usually reinforced by using thicker steel, but in this work the possibility of reinforcing the critical corners with composite patches was analyzed. These composite patches should reinforce the critical corners of balcony openings in order to reduce stress concentration. In this report, a typical detail of balcony opening has been observed in cases of hogging and sagging of global ship load cases.

The aim of the present study was to find the optimal configuration of composite patch. To find this, a parametric study has been performed: double-side patch and single-side patch, with two different composite materials, various thicknesses and stacking sequence, have been analyzed and compared.

The behaviour of the reinforcement system was investigated by numerical simulation, in terms of fatigue life analysis. Three different approaches for the fatigue study were taken: DNV Methodology using S-N curves for base material; a classical high cycle fatigue method with Goodman Correction for mean stresses; and a strain-life fatigue approach. Besides, finite element analysis was used to analyze the stress distribution within the laminates and predict first ply failure. In an attempt to more clearly understand the failure mechanisms within the bonded joint and to observe and predict the behaviour of the adhesive, the bond area was modelled and so evaluated by means of the Cohesive Zone Modelling (CZM) techniques.

1 INTRODUCTION

Balcony opening corners are prone to fatigue crack initiation due to the stress concentration found around geometry discontinuities. Thus these areas are always designed with a radius to smoothen out the discontinuities and often have to be reinforced to prevent cracking. These balcony corners are usually reinforced by using thicker steel but in this project the possibility of reinforcing the critical corners with composite patches was also analysed.

The idea of this task is to analyse several different patches in order to obtain the patch that mostly reduces stress in steel. Therefore a parametric study was done.

2 BALCONY OPENING CONCEPT. PATCH DESIGN.

As a starting point in numerical simulations of reinforcement of critical details of balcony openings with composite patches, CETENA delivered a part of a global ship model. In this model, stresses on a typical detail of balcony opening in cases of hogging and sagging of global ship model are observed (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

Figure 1 Detail of global ship in hogging condition

Figure 2 Detail of global ship in sagging condition

The goal of this task is to find the optimal configuration of composite patch. These composite patches should reinforce steel in places where maximum stresses occur i.e. in balcony opening corners. To provide a better engineering solution, double side patch has been used. Also, cases with patch on one side (outer side) have been analyzed because they are more cost efficient, easier to replace and allow the inspection of the metal substrate during the operational life of the structure. Furthermore, the solution with the patch on the external side does not require the adoption of a additional fire insulation system. The geometry of inner patch can be seen on Figure 3 and the geometry of outer patch on Figure 4.

Figure 3 Geometry of internal patch

Figure 4 Geometry of external patch

Twenty-four different cases have been analysed i.e. two materials, three thicknesses and three different ply layups have been varied. Also, cases have been divided by observing one side patch and double side patch. Work plan is shown in Table 1.

Case number	Short name	Shape	Material	One side / two sides	Thickness	Fibre orientation	Software FEM
1	A-M1-2S-t1-fo1	A	Material 1	Two side	t1	0°/90°	ANSYS
2	A-M1-2S-t1-fo2					45°/-45°	
3	A-M1-2S-t1-fo3					0°/45°/90°/135°	
4	A-M1-2S-t2-fo1				t2	0°/90°	
5	A-M1-2S-t2-fo2					45°/-45°	
6	A-M1-2S-t2-fo3					0°/45°/90°/135°	
7	A-M1-2S-t3-fo1			t3	0°/90°		
8	A-M1-2S-t3-fo2				45°/-45°		
9	A-M1-2S-t3-fo3				0°/45°/90°/135°		
10	A-M1-1S-t1-fo1			One side	t1	0°/90°	
11	A-M1-1S-t2-fo1				t2	0°/90°	
12	A-M1-1S-t3-fo1				t3	0°/90°	
13	A-M2-2S-t1-fo1	A	Material 2	Two side	t1	0°/90°	ABAQUS
14	A-M2-2S-t1-fo2					45°/-45°	
15	A-M2-2S-t1-fo3					0°/45°/90°/135°	
16	A-M2-2S-t2-fo1				t2	0°/90°	
17	A-M2-2S-t2-fo2					45°/-45°	
18	A-M2-2S-t2-fo3					0°/45°/90°/135°	
19	A-M2-2S-t3-fo1			t3	0°/90°		
20	A-M2-2S-t3-fo2				45°/-45°		
21	A-M2-2S-t3-fo3				0°/45°/90°/135°		
22	A-M2-1S-t1-fo1			One side	t1	0°/90°	
23	A-M2-1S-t2-fo1				t2	0°/90°	
24	A-M2-1S-t3-fo1				t3	0°/90°	

Table 1: Application cases

	Ply thickness (mm)	Number of plies	Thickness (mm)	Tapering (7°) length (mm)
t1	0.625	12	7.5	61
t2	0.625	18	11.25	92
t3	0.625	24	15	122

Table 2: Thickness of patches

Two different materials have been analysed: Vacuum Bagging Carbon/Vinylester and Carbon/Epoxy. Glass fibres have been rejected due to their low stiffness and the need for a very large thickness in order to get a notable reinforcement of the steel plate. Therefore, carbon fibres have been used instead. They allow relatively high stiffness while having a small thickness.

3 BALCONY OPENING CONCEPT. PATCH DESIGN.

In this work, a numerical simulation based in finite element method (FEM) to find hybrid joint behaviour has been used. The tests were then numerically modelled in a 3D space within both ANSYS and ABAQUS commercial finite element software. The first software was used to analyse the patch with the material 1 whereas the second one was simulate the behaviour of the patch with the material 2. Main characteristics of the numerical models are listed below:

- Both steel structure and patch has been discretized using shell elements (a 4-node doubly curved general-purpose shell finite membrane strains), with the edge size of 20 mm and in balcony corners. The size of composite element is 10 mm.
- Beam elements (2-node linear beam in space, which has six degrees of freedom at each node) with negligible cross section (only 0.01 mm² in order not to violate the rigidity of the model) have been placed on curved edges, and so to observe stresses on edges since crack initiation is expected there.
- In order to account for the geometrical and material nonlinearities, the Newton-Raphson method has been utilized together with a line search algorithm.
- Analysis options: automatic step time increment, max TS = 0.1·d_{fin}, min TS = 1E-8·d_{fin}, max. number of increments = 2000.

3.1 Material properties

The Carbon/Epoxy patches would be fabricated using CST 200 carbon fibers with area density equal to 200 g/m² provided by SGL GROUP. The matrix system consists of LH 160 133 epoxy resin and H 138 hardener, provided by HAVEL.

The Carbon/Vinyl-ester patches would be fabricated using L(X) 440-C10 [0]2 carbon fabric. The two layers are stitched together and the individual weight density of each layer is 208 g/m². The carbon fabric is provided by AMT DEVOLD. The resin selected was DION 9500-M800 vinylester resin provided by REICHHOLD.

The steel is a mild steel AH36 (6, 8, 10 and 12mm thick, depending on different areas of the component).

Composite material has been defined as orthotropic elastic material and its failure has been observed through both Tsai-Wu and Tsai-Hill failure criteria.

For sake of simplicity, steel material has been defined as isotropic elastic material.

All materials have been undergone a complete characterization through different testing campaigns, carried out under the framework of the MOSAIC project. Material properties assigned to the FE model are shown in Table 3.

	AH36 Steel	Vacuum bagging, carbon fibre/epoxi	Vacuum bagging, carbon fibre/vinylester
Law	Elastic isotropic	Elastic orthotropic <i>Note: Tsai-Wu failure criteria</i>	Elastic orthotropic <i>Note: Tsai-Hill failure criteria</i>
Properties	E = 209220 MPa ν = 0.2734 Yielding stress = 393.4 MPa UTS = 524.4 MPa Elongation to failure = 32.5%	E ₁₁ = 102600 MPa E ₂₂ = 7600 MPa E ₃₃ = 7600 MPa ν ₁₂ = 0.488 ν ₁₃ = 0.26 ν ₃₂ = 0.488 G ₁₂ = 4500 MPa G ₂₃ = 3015 MPa G ₃₁ = 4500 MPa	E ₁₁ = 112290 MPa E ₂₂ = 5500 MPa E ₃₃ = 5500 MPa ν ₁₂ = 0.376 ν ₁₃ = 0.591 ν ₃₂ = 0.376 G ₁₂ = 2000 MPa G ₂₃ = 1200 MPa G ₃₁ = 2000 MPa
Reference	Ref. [2]	Ref [3]	Ref [3]

Table 3: Material properties

3.2 Boundary conditions and loads

Boundary conditions and loads have been transferred from the global ship model to the local refined model using the submodeling technique. This activity has been carried out following the Lloyd's Register procedure, Ref [4]. The displacements obtained from the global FE model, loaded both in hogging and sagging condition, are applied at the boundaries of the local refined model in form

of imposed displacements. The loads which applied to the global model are the still water loads and the wave loads (with a probability occurrence of 10^{-8}).

3.3 Adhesive joints: bonded interfaces

A Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) is used to model the adhesive behaviour including the debonding phenomenon. CZM is based on the assumption that one or multiple fracture interface can be artificially introduced in structures, in which damage growth is allowed by the introduction of a possible discontinuity in the displacement field.

One tool was used for the simulation of the interface material failures:

- Surface-based cohesive behaviour.

The formulae and laws that govern cohesive surface behaviour are very similar to those used for cohesive elements with traction-separation constitutive behaviour:

- linear elastic traction-separation,
- damage initiation criteria, and
- damage evolution laws.

The traction-separation model used assumes initially linear elastic behaviour followed by the initiation and evolution of damage. The elastic behaviour is written in terms of an elastic constitutive matrix that relates the normal and shear stress to the normal and shear separations across the interface.

Once a damage initiation criterion is met, damage can occur according to a user-defined damage evolution law. In this case study, damage is assumed to initiate when a quadratic interaction function involving the nominal stress ratios is fulfilled.

The adhesive layer is most likely mixed mode loaded, i.e. we have a contribution of Mode I and Mode II in the failure process. The damage propagation is studied in terms of energy release rate and fracture toughness.

However, it is important to recognize that damage in surface-based cohesive behaviour is an interaction property, not a material property. Traction and separation are interpreted differently for cohesive elements and cohesive surfaces:

	cohesive elements	cohesive surfaces
separation	nominal strain (ϵ) = relative displacement (d) between top & bottom of the cohesive layer / Initial thickness (T_0)	contact separation (d)
traction	nominal stress (s)	contact stress (t) = contact force (F) / Current area (A) at each contact point

Table 4: Differences between cohesive elements and cohesive surfaces

Since there is just one possible interface, one bilinear cohesive law is used. The CZM properties are defined to get the strength limits indicated in Table 5.

Cohesive properties	Steel / Composite
Normal stress (MPa)	18.1
Tangential stress (MPa)	17.1
Critical fracture energy for normal (mode I) separation (N/mm)	1.667
Critical fracture energy tangential (mode II) slip (N/mm)	1.784
Reference	Ref. [5]

Table 5: Interfaces cohesive properties

4 FATIGUE ANALYSIS.

Since the crack initiation is expected on the edges of the steel, the axial stresses in beam elements are directly used to the fatigue study.

Firstly, the case without composite patches has been analysed. Then, the cases with different patch configurations have been analysed and compared. The aim was to determine the patch that provides the most reduction of the stresses in steel. Later, the fatigue analysis of the steel structure has been made.

Three different approaches have been compared in this report.

3.1 DNV Fatigue Assessment Approach

In first approach, the fatigue analysis is based on the use of S-N fatigue resistance curve for the base material, i.e. non-welded steel. S-N curve marked III is taken according to DNV “Fatigue Assessment of ship structures” [7]; section 2.4. The fatigue resistance curve is given as:

$$\log N = \log \bar{a} - m \cdot \log \Delta \sigma \quad (1)$$

where N is the predicted number of cycles to failure for the specific stress range $\Delta \sigma$, m is negative inverse slope of S-N curve and $\log \bar{a}$ is the intercept of $\log N$ -axis by S-N curve. The parameters $\log \bar{a}$ and m are taken from Table 2-1 for base material III [7]. The values are:

$$\log \bar{a} = 15.117; m = 4.0 \quad (2)$$

According to Section 2.3.4 [7], the stress range in the base material can be reduced in comparison to the case of the welded joints. The calculated stress range $\Delta \sigma$ is then multiplied with the reduction factor f_m before establishing the number of cycles, N , from the S-N curve. The reduction factor f_m is given as:

$$f_m = \frac{\sigma_t + 0.6 \cdot |\sigma_c|}{\sigma_t + |\sigma_c|} \quad (3)$$

where σ_t is the tension stress, σ_c is the compression stress and σ_{static} is the mean stress, according to:

$$\sigma_t = \max \begin{cases} \sigma_{static} + 0.5 \cdot \Delta \sigma \\ 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_c = \min \begin{cases} \sigma_{static} - 0.5 \cdot \Delta \sigma \\ 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{static} = 0.5 \cdot (\sigma_{max} + \sigma_{min}) \quad (6)$$

The results of the fatigue analysis for all cases, including the case without patch, are given in Table 6. The stresses in hogging and sagging conditions are given as the axial stresses in the beam elements on the rounded edge of the balcony opening. Five beam elements have been taken at which the greatest stress range occurs. Then, the fatigue life has been calculated for that five elements and the number of cycles is taken as the minimum number of cycles from 5 elements.

3.2 High Cycle Fatigue Classical Method with Goodman Correction

Another approach, based on High cycle fatigue classical method with Goodman correction [8], in which S-N curve for the material is estimated from empirical data, assumes that the endurance limit

for steel material is defined as the stress that causes failure at 106 loading cycles. The endurance limit or fatigue limit represents a stress level below which the material is assumed not fail and can be cycled infinitely. For steel, it can be approximated by:

$$S_{s,steel} \approx 0.5 \cdot S_u ; \text{ for } S_u < 1400 \text{ MPa} \quad (7)$$

where S_u is ultimate strength of steel. In addition, the stress level corresponding to 1000 cycles, S_{1000} , can be approximated by:

$$S_{1000,steel} \approx 0.9 \cdot S_u \quad (8)$$

A generalized S-N curve for wrought steels can be created by connecting the S_{1000} point with the endurance limit S_e . According to this S-N curve, the S-N slope and the S-N intercept are given as:

$$\text{slope} = -\frac{1}{3} \log\left(\frac{S_{1000}}{S_e}\right) = -0.085 \quad (9)$$

$$\text{intercept} = \log\left(\frac{S_{1000}^2}{S_e}\right) = 2.9 \quad (10)$$

Then, the number of cycles, N, can be calculated as:

$$\log N = \frac{1}{\text{slope}} \log S_a - \frac{\text{intercept}}{\text{slope}} \quad (11)$$

where S_a is the stress amplitude, i.e. half stress range. According to Goodman [8], stress amplitude is replaced with:

$$\frac{S_a}{1 - \frac{S_m}{S_u}} \quad (12)$$

where S_m is the mean stress. The number of cycles calculated by this second approach are given in the Table 6, and compared with the approach from DNV.

Reference		Case name	Stress in hogging (MPa)	Stress in sagging (MPa)	N by DNV [7](cycles)	Increase of fatigue life (%)	N by [8](cycles)	Increase of fatigue life [%]
		No patch	476.92	-295.21	7155	-	1104	
Double side patch	Material 1	A-M1-2S-t1-fo1	456.54	-288.72	8323	16,33%	1781	61,32%
		A-M1-2S-t1-fo2	444.58	-272.89	9561	33,63%	2436	120,65%
		A-M1-2S-t1-fo3	444.64	-278.69	9342	30,57%	2399	117,30%
		A-M1-2S-t2-fo1	451.99	-285.36	8680	21,32%	1992	80,43%
		A-M1-2S-t2-fo2	438.40	-266.31	10225	42,91%	3600	226,09%
		A-M1-2S-t2-fo3	434.51	-272.43	10240	43,12%	3095	180,34%
		A-M1-2S-t3-fo1	447.13	-281.94	9076	26,85%	2247	103,53%
		A-M1-2S-t3-fo2	433.04	-263.34	10729	49,96%	3286	197,64%
		A-M1-2S-t3-fo3	426.62	-267.30	11027	54,12%	3789	243,21%

	Material 2	A-M2-2S-t1-fo1	462.97	-286.25	8067	12,75%	1542	39.67%
		A-M2-2S-t1-fo2	449.74	-270.46	9332	30,43%	2169	96.47%
		A-M2-2S-t1-fo3	450.48	-280.50	8930	24,81%	2085	88.86%
		A-M2-2S-t2-fo1	460.27	-286.83	8187	14,43%	1639	48.46%
		A-M2-2S-t2-fo2	447.09	-269.49	9532	33,23%	2314	109.60%
		A-M2-2S-t2-fo3	440.74	-274.29	9752	36,30%	2659	140.85%
		A-M2-2S-t3-fo1	457.68	-280.56	8525	19,15%	1762	59.60%
		A-M2-2S-t3-fo3	435.13	-262.94	10595	48,08%	3129	183.42%
Single side patch	Material 1	A-M1-1S-t1-fo1	456.94	-290.94	8232	15,05%	1757	59.15%
		A-M1-1S-t2-fo1	454.33	-289.53	8415	17,61%	1871	69.47%
		A-M1-1S-t3-fo1	450.73	-291.71	8539	19,35%	2024	83.33%
	Material 2	A-M2-1S-t1-fo1	461.41	-287.61	8105	13,28%	1595	44.47%
		A-M2-1S-t2-fo1	458.78	-289.16	8193	14,51%	1690	53.08%
		A-M2-1S-t3-fo1	455.83	-287.52	8399	17,39%	1815	64.40%

Table 6: Number of cycles to failure results

Table 6 presents two different approaches based on S-N curves, i.e. DNV [7] and approach from Ref. [8]. It is obvious that the estimated increase of the fatigue life is larger when approach from [8] is used. The difference between these assessments is caused by different assumption of the slopes of the S-N curves. Comparing these two approaches, relation between DNV slope (m) and slope from second approach (slope) is given by:

$$m = -\frac{1}{\text{slope}} \quad (19)$$

According to this relation, slope in the approach from [8] is 11.76 and in DNV approach is 4. Therefore, the difference is not unexpected.

From the results in Table 6, it can be seen that the case with the thickest double-sided patch and with the layers orientation $0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/135^\circ$ can withstand the highest number of cycles before failure. Although, the patch with this stacking sequence and with the material No.1 seems to be the best one, outer composite patch doesn't satisfy Tsai Wu failure criteria. Therefore, for material No. 1, the case with the thickest double-sided patch and with the layer orientation $0^\circ/90^\circ$ seems the most promising.

Figure 5 Tsai-Wu failure criteria for patch configuration No.9.

3.3 Uniaxial strain-life fatigue analysis

Although the component should be designed so that stresses and strains are below the elastic limit under normal service loading, we know that yielding occur at the local area of interest and indeed must do if fatigue cracks are to initiate. For that reason, it has been considered that the application of the strain-life approach would be more appropriated in this case.

The procedure followed for this approach is explained below, Ref. [9]:

- i. Stress results from a linear elastic FEA.
- ii. Since the stress tensor represents an uniaxial stress state, the principal stress can be converted into elastic-plastic stress-strain using Neuber's rule.
- iii. Stresses obtained by FEA are directly local stresses, so it is not needed to apply any elastic stress concentrator factor.
- iv. The local strain history is used in the strain-life fatigue calculation and the associated stresses are used to apply a mean stress correction (Coffin-Manson's equation with Morrow's mean stress correction).

The relationship (Conffin-Manson's equation) between true stress amplitude and endurance is:

$$\Delta\varepsilon/2 = \left(\frac{\sigma'_f}{E} \right) (2N_f)^b + \varepsilon'_f (2N_f)^c \quad (20)$$

Morrow's mean stress correction is:

$$\Delta\varepsilon/2 = \left(\frac{\sigma'_f - \sigma_m}{E} \right) (2N_f)^b + \varepsilon'_f (2N_f)^c \quad (20)$$

Seven material properties have been used in the previous equations, Ref [10].

E	the elastic modulus (Young's Modulus)	209220	MPa	
K'	the strain hardening coefficient	694,00	MPa	approx equal sigf/ef^n
n'	the strain hardening exponent	0,112	-	approx equal to b/c
b	the fatigue strength exponent (Basquin exponent)	-0,08263	-	range -0.05 to -0.12
σ'_f	the fatigue strength coefficient	869,40	MPa	can be estimated from UTS: $\sigma'_f = \sigma_u + 345$ MPa
c	the fatigue ductility exponent (the Coffin-Manson exponent)	-0,73779	-	relatively narrow range of c of -0,50 to -0,80 for most engineering materials
ε'_f	the fatigue ductility coefficient	0,279524	-	approx equal to true fracture strain

Table 8: Number of cycles to failure results

The stresses, in hogging and sagging conditions, are given as the axial stresses in the beam elements on the rounded edge of the balcony opening. Five beam elements have been taken at which the greatest stress range occurs. Then, the fatigue life has been calculated for that five elements and the number of cycles from Table 9 is taken as the minimum number of cycles from 5 elements.

		Case name	Stress in hogging (MPa)	Stress in sagging (MPa)	N (cycles)	Increase of fatigue life (%)
Reference		No patch	476.92	-295.21	3016	-
Double side patch	Material 1	A-M1-2S-t1-fo1	456.54	-288.72	4071	34,98%
		A-M1-2S-t1-fo2	444.58	-272.89	5641	87,04%
		A-M1-2S-t1-fo3	444.64	-278.69	5337	76,96%
		A-M1-2S-t2-fo1	451.99	-285.36	4485	48,71%
		A-M1-2S-t2-fo2	438.40	-266.31	6555	117,34%
		A-M1-2S-t2-fo3	434.51	-272.43	6755	123,97%
		A-M1-2S-t3-fo1	447.13	-281.94	4865	61,31%
		A-M1-2S-t3-fo2	433.04	-263.34	7118	136,01%
		A-M1-2S-t3-fo3	426.62	-267.30	7685	154,81%
	Material 2	A-M2-2S-t1-fo1	462.97	-286.25	3810	26,33%
		A-M2-2S-t1-fo2	449.74	-270.46	5321	76,43%
		A-M2-2S-t1-fo3	450.48	-280.50	4865	61,31%
		A-M2-2S-t2-fo1	460.27	-286.83	3933	30,40%
		A-M2-2S-t2-fo2	447.09	-269.49	5598	85,61%
		A-M2-2S-t2-fo3	440.74	-274.29	5907	95,86%
		A-M2-2S-t3-fo1	457.68	-280.56	4306	42,77%
		A-M2-2S-t3-fo2	442.71	-267.93	6071	101,29%
		A-M2-2S-t3-fo3	435.13	-262.94	6836	126,66%
Single side patch	Material 1	A-M1-1S-t1-fo1	456.94	-290.94	3980	31,96%
		A-M1-1S-t2-fo1	454.33	-289.53	4072	35,01%
		A-M1-1S-t3-fo1	450.73	-291.71	4324	43,37%
	Material 2	A-M2-1S-t1-fo1	461.41	-287.61	3849	27,62%
		A-M2-1S-t2-fo1	458.78	-289.16	3939	30,60%
		A-M2-1S-t3-fo1	455.83	-287.52	4071	34,98%

Table 9: Number of cycles to failure results

As seen, that the obtained fatigue life results with this approach are slightly different. However, note that the trend is the same in the three approaches.

5 ADHESIVE ANALYSIS.

The numerical analyses provide insight into the behaviour and the failure mechanism present in the adhesive joint. Two variables have been used in this report to study this behaviour:

1. CSQUADSCRT (Quadratic stress-based damage initiation criterion for cohesive surfaces). In this case study, damage is assumed to initiate when a quadratic interaction function involving the nominal stress ratios is fulfilled.
2. CSDMG (Damage variable for cohesive surfaces): value of the variable scale of the damage, D. This variable is zero if not satisfied any criterion of initial damage, value between 0 and 1 during the evolution of damage and unit value when the adhesive is completely degraded.

The CSQUADSCRT plot, for the configuration (with material No.2) that have shown the greatest improvement in increasing fatigue life, is presented in Figure 6. Besides, the failure criteria index in inner and outer patch are plotted for these cases in both hogging and sagging condition.

Analyzing the results it can be seen that the study of the results obtained for CSQUADSCRT and CSDMG variables shows that, overall, no adhesive failure occurs.

Figure 6 Case A-M2-2S-t3-fo3 (Outer Patch)

6 CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this analysis was to find the optimal configuration of composite patch. These composite patches should reinforce the critical corners of balcony openings in order to reduce stress concentration. To find the best configuration of patch, a parametric study has been made. Double-side patch and single side patch with various thicknesses and fiber orientations have been analyzed and compared.

Failure in composite material has been observed through both Tsai-Hill and Tsai-Wu failure criteria. For patches Carbon/Vinyl ester material, results have shown that only the cases with fiber orientation $0^\circ/90^\circ$ satisfy those criteria. Whereas, in cases with Carbon/Epoxy patches, all configurations satisfy both failure criteria.

A Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) is [1] used to model the adhesive behaviour including the debonding phenomenon. The CZM technique implemented in the commercial finite element software, both ANSYS and ABAQUS have been successfully used to simulate the thin strip of adhesive of the bonded interface. The numerical analyses have provided insight into the failure mechanism present in the adhesive joint, showing that debonding doesn't occur between the steel structure and the composite reinforcements for all cases.

The aim of this report has been to determine the patch that provides the most reduction of the stresses in steel and therefore the fatigue analysis of the steel structure has been made. Three different approaches have been compared and they have given different results due to different slope of S-N and e-N curve but the same conclusions. They all have shown that the cases with the thickest double-sided patch can withstand the higher number of cycles before failure. Results have shown that the case with fibre orientation $0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/135^\circ$ can withstand the highest number of cycles and seems to be the most favourable case. However, in cases with Carbon/Vinylester material, the failure criterion in composite patch is not satisfied. Therefore, in this case, the configuration with the thickest double-sided patch and with the layers orientation $0^\circ/90^\circ$ is the most promising one. In conclusion, the characteristics of the most favourable cases are shown in table below:

Name	Shape	Material	One side / two sides	Thickness	Fibre orientation
A-M1-2S-t3-fo1	A	VB C/V	Two side	15 mm	0°/90°
A-M2-2S-t3-fo3	A	VB C/E	Two side	15 mm	0°/45°/90°/135°

Comparing the results of fatigue analysis for cases with fibre orientation 0°/90°, it can be seen that the increase of fatigue life for cases with double side patch is not much greater than for cases with single side patch. Therefore, the single side patch is more cost efficient and easier to replace and for that reason is recommended for practical use.

The characteristics of single-patches cases are listed in table below:

Name	Shape	Material	One side / two sides	Thickness	Fibre orientation
A-M1-1S-t3-fo1	A	VB C/V	One side	15 mm	0°/90°
A-M2-1S-t3-fo1	A	VB C/E	One side	15 mm	0°/90°

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